

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Effectiveness of principals' corrective approach on management of students' discipline in public secondary schools in Migori County, Kenya

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Abstract

This study investigated the effectiveness of corrective approach on student's discipline; establish effectiveness of corrective approach on students' discipline in public secondary schools in Migori County, Kenya. This study was informed by Operant and Erickson's theories. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design with a population consisting of 271 principals, 271 deputy principals, 271 student leaders, 1759 teachers and 10 Sub- County Directors of Education (SCD). 30% was used to select 74 principals, 74 deputy principals, 74 student leaders, 8 SCDs and 317 teachers from Krejci and Morgan table; a total of 547 respondents. Data was collected using 2 questionnaires; one for Administrators, and the other for teachers while an Interview guide to gather information from SCDs and FGD guide from student leaders. Piloting, involving 10% from each category of the respondents, was done to determine reliability and validity of the research tools. Test-retest method was used to establish reliability by employing Pearson's r with a reliability threshold of 0.70 and above. Face and content validity was determined by experts in Educational Management and Policy and determination of CVI at 0.85. Quantitative data was analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, means, standard deviation and T-test while qualitative data was coded, transcribed and organized thematically. Research ethics were observed during both data collection and reporting of findings. The study established that the corrective approach was effective (Mean = 2.90) and had a statistically significant relationship with management of student discipline. Findings are important to educational administrators, policy makers and planners in understanding how preventive, corrective and positive behavior reinforcement approaches are effective on management of students' discipline. The study recommends that there should be guidelines for training peer counselors, integrating withdrawal of privileges to be part of rules and regulations, there should be a vote head for the BOM to reward and give certificates to students with outstanding positive behavior also to develop a working collaboration between parents and teachers for effective management of students' discipline.

Keywords: Management; Discipline; Corrective; Approaches; Students

1. Introduction

The importance of discipline management in schools has gained prominence in the wake of increases in various forms of indiscipline among learners (Mendels, 2012). Available literature shows a sharp increase in incidences of indiscipline in schools globally, as manifested through destruction of school property, drug abuse, sexual relations, stealing, lateness, and truancy, violence, and gang affiliations, among others. Even though the rise in cases of indiscipline in schools appears to be global, Africa bears the brunt of school indiscipline, as reported by Kelley and Peterson (2017). The rapid increase in cases of indiscipline in schools in Africa is attributed to various factors, including the influence of the information and electronic revolution, Blomberg (2012). The apparent emergence of more permissive parenting and large scale banning of corporal punishment and adoption of alternative forms of punishment, which is seen as time consuming and ineffective, with learners and teachers facing compliance challenges (Alawi, 2011). Consequently, there is general consensus on the need to re-examine the current thinking on school discipline management (Kelley and

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Peterson, 2017; Maguire, Ball and Braun, 2010) focusing on three broad paradigms to discipline management in schools - preventive; corrective and positive reinforcement approaches. This study takes a critical look at the corrective approaches to managing learners' discipline in schools. Discipline management molds, corrects, strengthens or perfects behavior and it is achieved when sound leadership is applied using positive motivation (McArdle 2011).

Management of students' discipline in public secondary schools in Kenya has been a concern (Akande, 2015; Modis and Yambo, 2015; Kute 2015). In the past decade, Secondary schools in Kenya have witnessed upsurge in discipline cases among students. For instance, a Task Force Report on Student Discipline working between June and July of 2012 observed that violent strikes affected more than 300 secondary schools in the country (Njoroge and Nyabuto 2014). It has been in the records that between 2007-2016, a total of 347 arson cases were reported by the Cabinet Secretary for Education (Republic of Kenya, 2018) 127 in 2017 and 164 cases in 2018 where 26 cases are from Nyanza region, currently forming Migori, Homa Bay, Niemira, Kisii, Siaya and Kisumu counties (Republic of Kenya, 2018). Despite the Teachers Services Commission (TSC) circular no: 3/2010 and Code of Conduct and Ethics (2015) on child protection, between 2010-2017 there had been training of school administrators by Kenya Education Management Institute (KEMI) yet the country still witnessed cases of sexual harassment, drug abuse and rampage of students have been on the rise. Since 2018, over 134 schools burnt have been experienced. According to Sachiyo and Yambo (2020) the government of Kenya through ministry of Education set official operating hours for all day, public or private secondary Institutions to be from Monday to Friday- as from 8.00 a.m. to 3.30 p.m. for class hours and 3.30 p.m. to 4.45 p.m. for co-curricular activities (Moe, 2015). In the whole country there were records for 144 indiscipline cases between June and July 2018; in coastal region of 14 schools, western 38, (Migori had 18 cases). Rift valley 17, Nairobi 16, North Eastern 12, Eastern 08, Central 21 (RoK, 2018). This indicated that schools all over the country had a challenge with regard to students' discipline despite various approaches used to address it. It is on this basis that the study sought to establish the effectiveness of school principals' corrective approach to managing students' discipline in Migori county Kenya, which other studies have not addressed.

1.1. Statement of the problem

Discipline management is an important element of educational management, and has received widespread attention globally, in view of a rapid increase in cases of indiscipline, especially in Africa. Whereas there is extensive discourse on discipline management revolving around the various approaches, there appears to be a lack of consensus on the best approach. To further complicate this, the policies and procedures that have been developed and put in place by the Ministry of Education in Kenya to guide discipline management in schools, appear to draw a delicate balance between the three broad approaches. The policy framework therefore places the burden on school heads, to find a balance and adopt the best possible approach, depending on the circumstances. Evidently, school heads in Kenya are applying different approaches, and meeting with varying success, going by the available statistics on cases of indiscipline in schools, which show some skewedness across the country. For instance, Migori County, where this study was situated, recorded more incidences on indiscipline, compared to other counties in Kenya (MoE, 2018). Since 2014, Migori county has witnessed an increase trend in cases of strikes, arson, rape, exam cheating, molestation and destruction of property (TSC Migori County Education Office, 2018).

1.2. Objectives of the Study

- To establish the effectiveness of corrective approach on management of students' discipline in public secondary schools in Migori County

1.3. Research Questions

- To what extent is corrective approach effective on management of students' discipline in public secondary schools in Migori County?

1.4. Research Hypothesis

- Ho1: There is no statistically significant relationship between teachers and administrators views on corrective approach and management of student's discipline in public secondary schools in Migori County, Kenya.

2. Theoretical framework

Many theories address administrative roles within the learning institutions advanced by several authorities as a basis to improving students' discipline in secondary schools. This study was informed by behavior modification by operant theory (Skinner, 2005) which addresses human behavior through the law of effect. According to this theory, learning

depends on the events that occur after certain behavior and that learning what to do is gradual, not insightful. According to the law of effect, when in a given stimulus situation, a response is made and followed by a positive consequence, the response will tend to be repeated (Busienei, 2012). When followed by a negative consequence, this applies to punitive or corrective approach like suspension, expulsion and timeout it will tend not to be repeated. Skinner advanced the law of effect according to which behaviors that are rewarded tend to persist; this applies to positive behavior reinforcement approach like praises and rewards, while those that are followed by discomfort or punishment tend to diminish (Busienei, 2012). There is interconnectedness and people in the organization are clear as to who is to do what, how, why, when, and to what extent this approach has the potential to promote collective responsibility and accountability. In school situation teachers, parents and students would know the framework within which their responsibilities reside and the school principals would know overall accountability on school discipline. It was on this fact that preventive, corrective and positive behavior reinforcement approaches were attached to this theory. The theoretical framework of this study is also based on Erikson's theory on psychosocial stages of development which was developed by Ericson (1968). He argued that at adolescence stage, life gets more complex as one attempts to find his own identity, struggles with social interactions and grapples with moral issues. Most secondary school students are at this stage which is a volatile stage of human development and this may cause indiscipline (Chaplain, 2003). This is because if one is unsuccessful in navigating this stage, he experiences role confusion and upheaval (Blomberge, 2012). This theory is applicable in this study because students in public secondary schools are very much exposed to all sorts of behaviors in the society. Therefore, in an environment where leadership and guidance is not effectively offered, the discipline of the students becomes greatly jeopardized leading to an conducive working and learning environment.

2.1. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Relationships among independent, dependent and intervening variables

2.1.1. Source: Researchers' Own Conceptualization

Three types of variables are used in the conceptual framework; independent variables, intervening variable and dependent variable. Independent variable: corrective approaches like suspension, timeout and expulsion; the dependent variable that is management of students discipline as indicated in Figure 1 while the intervening variable, government policy, is to control the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The government's policy has a guideline for schools. The school principal has no power over this and s/he obliged to adhere to it. In this study, School Administration Guide (2018/2019), the Basic Education Act (2015), (2010), Republic of Kenya (2009) TSC Act (2013) and Heads Manual (2015) are the key government policy documents because they spell out guidelines in handling discipline issues in schools. They identify the areas of concern in students' discipline, the expected levels of competency and skills preparation, as well as planning and evaluation in order to attain student discipline.

3. Literature review

3.1. Effectiveness of the Corrective Approach on Students' Discipline Management

A study by Wright and Kate (2009) indicated that disruptive behavior was often the primary reason why students are placed in special education settings outside the general education classroom. Corrective strategies involve total rules around what is and isn't acceptable behavior within a school environment. They do not take into reason of any individual personal, educational, developmental, social or other circumstances and apply the consequences to any breach of the rules as stated. These policies can be administered in different ways but are generally founded on the belief that this sort of response to challenging behaviors fosters a sense of disciplinary equity and consistency within the school community. It's aimed at sending a clear message to all members about what behavior will and will not be tolerated, thus setting clear boundaries (Bejarano, 2014). Whereas the work of Wright and Kate (2009) dealt with violence and

indiscipline in schools, the current one dealt with the effectiveness of corrective approach on management of student's discipline to fill the research gap.

According to Daly (2013) study on Student suspensions a research review of Commission for children Tasmania. In Tasmania, the authority to discipline state school students is derived from the Education Act 1994. Tasmania's Department of Education has published Discipline Guidelines to provide guidance and procedures in relation to the application of the above legislated sanction. The Guidelines are to be read in the context of the Education Act and individual school discipline policies. For general purposes the following definitions are used in Tasmania. Detention is when a student is detained at school during recess, lunch time or after school, or excluded from regular classes, suspension is the temporary, full-time or part-time withdrawal of a student's right to attend school for a period of two weeks or less, on the authority of the principal, exclusion is the temporary full-time or part-time withdrawal of a student's right to attend school for a period of greater than two weeks, on the authority of the Secretary (delegated to Learning Services General Manager) while Expulsion is the full-time withdrawal of a student's right to attend a particular school, on the authority of the Secretary, expulsion from one school does not prohibit the enrolment of the student in another school (Adams, 2016).

In addition, Kambuga et al. (2018) carried out a study on Corporal Punishment as a Strategic Reprimand used by Teachers to curb Students' Misbehaviors in Secondary Schools a case in Tanzanian. It was found that despite the negative consequences that corporal punishment has on the students, it is commonly used in secondary schools in Tanzania. This study explicitly concludes that corporal punishment has impacts in several ways and those which are worth mentioning are: fear, physical harm, psychological impact, dropout/absenteeism and hatred towards teachers who use corporal punishment in schools. In addition to that, the study concludes that some students in the studied area quit schools because of rampant use of corporal punishment. Furthermore, the study found that the status of discipline in secondary schools was moderate (Nyagiati and Yambo, 2018). Use of corporal punishment was seen to be effective in mitigating students' disciplinary problems. It was further revealed that counseling and punishments that do not harm students physically could be used as alternatives to corporal punishments.

Further, Onyango et al. (2016) conducted a study on effectiveness of Exclusion in the Management of Student behaviour problems in Public Secondary Schools in Kenya. The quantitative findings revealed that there was a positive relationship between exclusion and management of student behavior problems. Additional study findings also established that exclusion was effective in managing student behavior problems since it was more appropriate for major offences and had reduced tension and strikes in schools. Further findings established that exclusion enhanced a sense of belonging in the students and developed rapport between the teacher and students. However, other respondents argued that exclusion stigmatized the learners, consumed time, increased resistance among learners and led to school dropout, therefore this study was to find out effectiveness of corrective approaches on management of students' discipline (Achiyo and Yambo, 2020). While Onyango et al. (2016) dealt with form four students, the current study dealt with student leaders to fill the research gap.

3.2. Effectiveness of expulsion on student discipline management

In the United States of America, Welsh and Little (2018) found out that the pathways, rates and correlates of exclusion due to school discipline in school discipline policies and practices in K-12 education which were associated with school exclusion have garnered substantial attention. Additionally, Ifeoma (2011) opined that the central role that school exclusion plays in discipline policies and practices, it is important to critically assess the pathways, rates, and harms associated with school exclusion. Their interest was to provides a systematic review of the interdisciplinary literature on the relationship between school exclusion and students' short- and long-term educational and life outcomes. Whereas a handful of possible pathways exist, the study identifies suspensions as most frequent pathway through which school discipline results in school exclusion. The results of this systematic review indicated that school exclusion is not an efficacious response to student misbehavior given the short and long term correlates with negative student educational and life outcomes (Reinke et al., 2007). There are several plausible mechanisms through which school exclusion may affects student outcomes but there was little empirical evidence on these mechanisms. Fixed period exclusion is one of the categories of exclusion recognized in the United Kingdom. It entails when a student is removed from school for a certain number of days during which they are required to stay away from the school premises. Permanent exclusion is another type of exclusion whereby a learner is removed from the institution in perpetuity. Whereas Welsh and Little (2018) dealt with caste and control in schools' discipline, the current study dealt with effectiveness of expulsion on student discipline to fill the research gap.

According to Hatton (2012), disciplinary exclusion is a strategy used by some schools in response to challenging behavior. The study explored factors within school ethos that may influence how challenging behavior is managed, to

identify differences in school ethos between excluding and non-excluding primary and junior schools in areas with the highest rates of social deprivation. Three focus groups and two interviews were initially conducted to identify factors that staff believed to be relevant to the inclusion and exclusion of pupils. Focus groups and interviews explored staff perceptions of practices in school and beliefs about inclusion and exclusion. Questionnaires were distributed to 16 schools and completed by 128 staff. Thematic analysis identified 13 themes, 10 of which indicated a difference in view between excluding and non-excluding schools. Multivariate analysis of variance indicated significant differences in responses between groups on the themes of responsibility, clarity, consistency, behavior management; Beliefs about inclusion and beliefs about reducing exclusion. These findings provide support for previous literature emphasizing the importance of some key features of school ethos in creating an inclusive environment (Arguedas et al., 2016).

The study done by Nagaratnam and Yeo, (2018) argued that expulsion from school is a life changing event and can leave a big scar in students' lives making them feel lost or miserable. This incident might change the direction of a student's life and whether the outcome is good or bad, will largely depend on the student. However, without keen intercession especially from parents, this interference in the students' lives might have an unsalvageable effect. This narrative case study aims to find out about an expelled girl's life once she left her old school where she was expelled from. The intention of this study is to understand how the respondent recognizes and overcomes her negative perception and emotions as an expelled student in the new school in regards to her psychosocial development. The findings obtained using qualitative interviewing, journal writing, and document analysis show four notable areas where the expelled student: expresses deep feeling of contrition after expulsion; managed their emotions by surrounding themselves in the company of people who offered them moral support like her parents, teachers and friends; parents were the most pivotal in helping and supporting their children to overcome the challenges they encountered; and the feeling that the disciplinary action taken in form of expulsion was unfair while supporting zero tolerance policies for serious offenses (Parzych et al., 2019).

3.3. Effectiveness of suspension in student discipline management

Study done by Vaccar (2010) proposed that suspension was a necessary component in the management of classroom discipline. This study provides a comprehensive review of literature on the contributors to racial, gender, and income disparities in disciplinary outcomes, and the extent to which emerging alternatives to exclusionary disciplinary approaches. They noted that although low-income and minority students experience suspensions and expulsions at higher rates than their peers, this disparity could be explained by school and classroom occurrences that result from the policies, practices, and perspectives of teachers and principals appear to play an important role in explaining the disparities. The same sentiments from Osterman (2010) also concluded that there are conceptual and open empirical questions on whether and how some of the various alternatives are working to counter the discipline disparities. Whereas the work of Vaccar (2010) dealt with the teachers' perceptions of the in-school suspension program, the current study dealt with effectiveness of suspension in student discipline to fill the research gap.

According to Morawska and Sanders (2011); the Ministry of Education (2015) suspension was not intended as a punishment. It is only one strategy for managing inappropriate behavior within a school's student welfare and discipline policies. It is most effective when it highlights the parents' responsibility for taking an active role, in partnership with the school, to modify the inappropriate behavior of their child. The school and the government school system will work with parents with a view to assisting a suspended student to re-join the school community as quickly as possible. Suspension also allows time for school personnel to plan appropriate support for the student to assist with successful re-entry. This may include access to appropriate support staff such as an Aboriginal community liaison officer or learning and support teacher. In some cases, suspension from school allows the school and government school system time to put measures in place to ensure the safety of students and staff.

The majority of students, as put forward by Adams (2016) suspension allows time for the student to reflect on their behavior, to acknowledge and accept responsibility for the behaviors which led to the suspension, and to accept responsibility for changing their behavior to meet the school's expectations in the future. Principals have authority, consistent with the provisions of these procedures and associated documents, to suspend or expel a student from their own school. They would exercise this authority having regard to their responsibilities to the whole school community and to the principles of procedural fairness on student's discipline (Akanke, 2015).

3.3.1. Effectiveness of time-out on students' discipline management

A study by Adie (2013), contends that use of suspensions and expulsions can lead to school drop outs as those being disciplined discontinue schooling, however, time-out when implemented correctly is an effective and positive discipline strategy with potential to enhance all aspects of the child's development and mental health. The appropriate use of time-out is also compatible with the needs of children with a history of exposure to trauma, the paper found. This study

focused on the influence of time out on younger children which is a departure from the present study (Al-Jarrah and Khazanah, 2013). While the work of Adie (2013) dealt with suspensions and expulsions that contributed to school dropouts, the current one dealt with effectiveness of time-out on students' discipline to fill the research gap.

Furthermore, a study by McLaurin-Jones and Kelly-Henry (2014) also came to the conclusion that generally, time-out is a moderately effective behavioral management intervention. However, it went further to clarify that it may be most effective for boys younger than 7 years for management of aggressive and non-compliant behavior. Nyagiati and Yambo (2018) postulated that time out has been widely advocated as an effective parental discipline practice to reduce disruptive and oppositional child behavior in young children. Despite evidence showing that the procedure is effective when used as part of a comprehensive positive parenting strategy it has not been uniformly accepted and critics have questioned its effectiveness and potentially adverse effects on parent-child relationship. The aim of Morawska and Sanders (2011) was to examine the controversy surrounding the use of time out, discusses the criticisms leveled against it, and concluded that its judicious use in parent training programs is justified and is of benefit to many children with conduct problems, however this study was to find out effectiveness of time out on management of student discipline to fill the research gap.

4. Research methodology

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design. The cross-sectional survey design was appropriate as it assisted the researcher to get the research data from individual principals, deputy principals, SCDs, teachers and student leaders. The survey is commonly used to study phenomena in social and psychological research, which was relevant to this study. It also allowed for use of mixed methods where quantitative and qualitative data was involved. In this study, this was achieved by collection of both qualitative and quantitative data by use of questionnaires, interview guide and Focus Group Discussion (FGD), which was then integrated in the presentation of study results (Creswell, 2013). This study was conducted in public secondary schools in Migori County, Kenya which is a cosmopolitan area consisting of Abasi, Kuria, Somalis, Luhya, Suba-Luos, Luos and a small number of Indians, Arabs, and Nubians, this makes it have influence of various cultural practices hence affects student's discipline. The study population consisted of 2582 respondents drawn from 271 principals, 271 deputy principals, 271 student leaders, 10 Sub County Directors (SCDs) and 1759 teachers, in Migori County. The sample size for this study was 547 respondents consisting of 148 administrators, 74 student leaders, 317 teachers and 8 SCDs. Simple random sampling was used to select principals and deputy principals; teachers, student leaders and SCDs involved in this study. According to Basic Education Act (2015), all disciplinary proceedings affecting a learner, the attendance of the Sub- County Education Officer shall be mandatory. This was why the SCDs were deemed fit for this study. Questionnaires were then administered to principals, deputy principals and teachers by the researcher after prior arrangement with them, over a period of one month. This was done by booking for their time prior to the delivery of questionnaires to the Administrators. After a period of one week, the completed questionnaires were collected. Follow up collection was done in the second week for those respondents who had not completed their questionnaires during the first collection visit. In addition, both interviews and Focus group discussions were done over a period of three weeks. The taped data from interviews and FGDs was later transcribed, and analyzed thematically. The researcher subjected the filled-up questionnaires to inspection and those missing data were separated from those that were fully filled. The questionnaires were keenly checked. When all the data had been keyed in, 20 questionnaires were selected randomly for verification of the SPSS program and correction done on the wrong entries. The data collected was analyzed using quantitative techniques by the use of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) Version 26, at the set p-value at .05 level of significance. Qualitative data was analyzed thematically where the responses from the interview schedule and focused group discussions organized into themes, meaning given and analysis done systematically, as guided by the objectives of the study. Analysis of quantitative data was done using both descriptive statistics comprising of frequency tables and figures and inferential statistics, used T-test analysis. Analysis of the study data involved both the quantitative and qualitative techniques. The mean ratings were then interpreted in agreement with (Cheruiyot and Sumata 2016) classification, using intervals as follows: 1.00-1.44 = not effective; 1.45 - 2.44 = lowly effective; 2.45 - 3.44 = effective; 3.45 - 4.44 = highly effective; 4.45 - 5.00 = very highly effective. The T-test was used to determine if there was a significant difference between the means groups.

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Effectiveness of Corrective Approach on Management of Students' Discipline

The second research question which was derived from the second objective of this study, which was to determine effectiveness of corrective approach on management of students' discipline in public secondary schools in Migori County. To meet the requirements of this objective and to test the set hypothesis, the respondents were to answer items

15-20 in the questionnaire. The responses were keyed into a computer data file and necessary calculations were done using SPSS version 26 programmed.

5.1.1. Vertical descriptive analysis of the classified respondents

The ratings of teachers and administrators on the level of effectiveness of the corrective approaches were done and presented in table 4.11 and table 4.12.

Table 1 Teachers Views on Level of Effectiveness of Corrective approaches

Corrective approach		Level Effectiveness					Total
		Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Time out of Indiscipline students	Frequency	44	50	61	33	13	201
	Percent	(21.9)	(24.9)	(30.3)	(16.4)	(6.5)	(100)
Use of Verbal Threats	Frequency	25	70	80	23	3	201
	Percent	(12.4)	(34.8)	(39.8)	(11.4)	(1.5)	(100)
Suspension of Indiscipline students from school	Frequency	19	38	56	49	29	201
	Percent	(9.4)	(18.9)	(27.9)	(24.4)	(14.4)	(100)
Expulsion of Indiscipline students	Frequency	33	46	51	46	25	201
	Percent	(14.4)	(22.9)	(25.4)	(22.9)	(12.4)	(100)
Withdrawal of privileges	Frequency	7	33	56	81	24	201
	Percent	(3.4)	(16.4)	(27.9)	(40.3)	(11.9)	(100)
Physical Punishment like Manual work	Frequency	24	44	54	44	43	201
	Percent	(11.9)	(21.9)	(26.9)	(21.9)	(21.4)	(100)

This table shows that teachers as respondents had regard on verbal threats at 39.8%, time out 30.3%, suspension of indiscipline students 27.9%, physical punishment like manual work 26.9% and expulsion of indiscipline students 25.4% as effective in the management of students' discipline in secondary schools. This approaches if properly used can effectively help in the management of secondary school students' discipline.

Majority of teachers as respondents rated withdrawal of privileges 40.3%. as highly effective in the management of students' discipline in secondary, this approach is seen as highly effective particularly when integrated into the school's administrative system. Administrators' views were also captured and presented on table 4.12 showing effectiveness of corrective approaches on management of students' discipline.

Table 2 Administrators' Views on Level of Effectiveness of Corrective approaches

Corrective approach		Effectiveness level					Total
		Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Time out of Indiscipline students	Frequency	9	27	48	23	14	121
	Percent	(7.4)	(23.3)	(39.7)	(19.0)	(11.6)	(100)
Use of Verbal Threats	Frequency	20	37	38	23	3	121
	Percent	(16.5)	(30.6)	(31.4)	(19.0)	(2.7)	(100)
Suspension of Indiscipline students from school	Frequency	10	21	48	34	8	121
	Percent	(8.3)	(17.4)	(39.7)	(28.1)	(6.6)	(100)
Expulsion of Indiscipline students	Frequency	16	24	43	23	15	95
	Percent	(13.2)	(19.8)	(35.5)	(19.0)	(12.4)	(100)
Withdrawal of privileges	Frequency	4	14	38	48	17	121
	Percent	(3.3)	(11.6)	(31.4)	(39.7)	(14.0)	(100)

Physical Punishment like Manual work	Frequency Percent	11 (9.1)	22 (18.2)	33 (27.3)	28 (23.1)	27 (22.3)	121 (100)
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Table 4.12 shows that administrators as respondents had time out 39.7%, suspension of indiscipline students 39.7%, verbal threats at 31.4%, expulsion of indiscipline students 35.5% and physical punishment like manual work 27.3% as effective in the management of students' discipline in secondary schools. They rated withdrawal of privileges 39.7% as highly effective. Both respondents rated the corrective approaches at almost the same rate showing they both use the approaches to manage discipline in schools.

The administrators had their views on how this can be enhanced as emerged in the interview schedule that SC2 noted;

According to me, is that physical punishment to the student because if you go the ways of expulsion or being expelled from school, some students enjoy going home so they will do mistakes to go home.

It also shows that administrators noted that withdrawal of privileges at 39.7% and teachers 40.3% as highly effective particularly when integrated into the school's administrative system this is observed by Kiggundu (2009) who argues that there is need for withdrawal of privileges' and should be done uniformly as a discipline code which will assist parents, students and other stakeholders to appreciate the effectiveness of punishment in schools. An analysis of the specific corrective approaches was done based on comparative views of teachers and administrators. The findings and the t-test results which compared the views of the two groups are shown in table 4.13

Table 3 Independent Samples t-test on Types of Corrective Approaches between Teachers' and Administrators

Corrective approach	Respondent	MR	Overall MR	t-test	Sig. (2-tailed)
Time out for Indiscipline Students	Teachers	2.61		t (316) =-13.906, p=.000	
	Administrators	3.01	2.75		
Use of Verbal Threats	Teachers	2.16		t (313) =-8.281, p=.000	
	Administrators	2.55	2.28		
Suspension of students from school	Teachers	3.13		t (314) =-20.445, p=.000	
	Administrators	3.03	3.10		
Expulsion of Indiscipline students	Teachers	2.95		t (312) =-15.824, p=.000	
	Administrators	2.99	2.97		
Withdrawal of Privileges	Teachers	3.36	3.37	T (312) =-26.403	
	Administrators	3.38			
Physical Punishment like manual work	Teachers	3.27		t (315) =-19.993, p=.000	
	Administrators	3.34	3.30		

Interpretation of Mean Rating; 1.00-1.44 = Not Effective; 1.45-2.44= Lowly Effective; 2.45-3.44 = Effective; 3.45-4.44 = Highly Effective; 4.45-5.00= Very Highly Effective

This shows the various corrective approaches and their level of effectiveness in the management of students' discipline in secondary schools. In terms of mean rating, the effective approaches are: withdrawal of privileges administrators mean rating at 3.38 while teachers mean rating at 3.36, this shows that this method is effective, using physical punishment like manual work, teachers mean rating 3.27 and administrators 3.34 and suspension of indiscipline students from school teachers rating at 3.13 while administrators mean rating 3.03 this shows that they are effective. However, the rest of corrective approaches in management of students' discipline had a mean rating of 2.9 and below, this still shows that they are effective in the management of discipline in secondary schools.

5.2. Hypothesis 2 Test

Ho1: There is no statistically significant relationship between teachers and administrators views on management of student's discipline in public secondary schools in Migori County.

The findings shows that the observed difference between the mean ratings of teachers and Administrators views is statistically significant, in all the corrective approaches since p=.000, The resulting or observed p values are .000 for all

the variable groups. Since this is below the critical p-value (.05), there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis and hence accept the alternative hypothesis. This therefore shows that there is statistically significant relationship between corrective approach and management of student's discipline in public secondary schools in Migori County. The higher the mean rating given by the respondents for each of the corrective approaches investigated, the higher the effectiveness of that approach in management of students' discipline in secondary schools.

5.2.1. Discussions on corrective approaches on management of student discipline

Study findings on effectiveness of time out of indiscipline students shows teachers rating at 2.61 and administrators 3.00 this approved time out of indiscipline students from school as an effective corrective approach on management of students' discipline as also observed by majority of the respondents who responded qualitatively like SC 2 who noted;

This can be effective to some extent because the isolated students will feel left out and may desire to change in order to be part of others and staying out of class for a while was expected to affect behavior change among the students. Students are asked to go out to the field and make noise there, if they were making noise in class. Also, Students who sleep in class are sent out to do some work.

5.2.2. S18 further agreed

It's a very highly effective approach however the psychological character of the student should be understood by the principal or the student might end up committing suicide.

According to Nkabinde (2007), time-out is sending the learner outside or to another classroom for a specific time where he / she will be with learners he/she is not used to, and this makes some learners feel isolated and may stop misbehaving. In the context of the present study, temporary withdrawal from class meant that students who had engaged in disciplines were sent out of class temporarily. Temporary withdrawal from class was used in managing student disciplines, as was cited by SC3 that,

Students who engage in indiscipline are asked to stay out of class for a while. This implies that staying out of class for a while was expected to be effective on behavior change among the students.

5.2.3. S16 who had a similar opinion said,

Students are asked to go out to the field and make noise there, if they were making noise in class. Students who sleep in class are sent out to do some work.

All the respondents seemed to concur that time out from class was used in managing student discipline. Similarly, Ifeoma (2011) concurs that effective classroom management techniques include, among others, constant engagement of students in activities, use of innovative instructional strategies and time out for misbehavior.

Also, study by Adie (2013) contends that use of suspensions and expulsions can lead to school drop outs as those being disciplined discontinue schooling, however, time-out when implemented correctly is an effective and positive discipline strategy with potential to enhance all aspects of the child's development and mental health. The appropriate use of time-out is also compatible with the needs of children with a history of exposure to trauma.

Furthermore, a study by McLaurin-Jones and Kelly-Henry (2014) also concluded that generally, time-out is a moderately effective behavioral management intervention. However, Mazinaw and Elinda (2012) in Nigeria found that sending pupils out of class as an unacceptable form of punishment. Also, Maphosa (2011) in South Africa established that the use of disciplinary measures like sending learners out of classroom is punitive in nature.

In this study, evidence further confirms that time out remains an effective approach to discipline of students. It is seen as an isolation and this may affect their psychology as they sit alone. It is necessary to use time out considering the type of offence, age and sex of the student for effective management of student discipline.

Similarly, findings on effectiveness of expulsion and suspension of indiscipline students as a corrective method, shows that teachers rating at 2.95 and administrators mean rating 2.99 this approved expulsion of indiscipline students from school as an effective corrective approach to manage students' discipline, while suspension teachers mean rating 3.13 administrator mean rating 3.03, they consider suspension of indiscipline students effective

Most of the responses that came from the interviews with regard to expulsion and suspension included the following;

5.2.4. S7 said

there is suspension and expulsions. So, there is when someone does something wrong is given suspension. But then these suspensions also have limits. Like there is no 3rd suspension, for the 3rd time you just go away.

5.2.5. S8 Also added

Ok, to me there are some measures the principals take to correct the mistake of the students. (i) By suspending the student who has done mistakes to go home and may be come back with their parents, so that they discuss on how to help such student. (ii) If the case is so serious, some are even expelled out of school, and send him/her away to go for good.

5.2.6. S10 added

According to me, I think the best way is through suspension, because the student will lose a lot when he is away. So will think of others and that will help him/her prevent being indisciplined

Findings by Vacar (2010) also established that School Suspension program was an effective and necessary tool to help for classroom management because it improved attendance and kept students up to pace with very little limitations. However, Bejarano (2014) argues that removing students from classroom removes them from meaningful educational opportunities that affect their future stating that exclusionary discipline is not equitable and leaves some students at a marked disadvantage. Golomb (2010) explains that exclusionary measures that have been associated with negative student outcome need to be reconsidered on their discipline practices and policies this was noted by qualitative responses like S9 who indicated;

I think another way is through suspension for example, if a student has made a mistake, he/ she will be suspended. So, others will be afraid, when she comes back to school, she will be disciplined because of being afraid of suspension again.”

This was further supported by MoE (2015) which states that suspension should not be solely intended as a punishment, and only one strategy for managing inappropriate behavior within a school's student welfare and discipline policies.

The current study reveals that suspension is an effective corrective method to manage student discipline; it gives shame to the suspended student hence a lesson to the rest of the students not to misbehave. It also works well when parents get time to introspect and participate in this process by giving support and advice to their children to help them improve in their behavior. The duration of suspension should be that stipulated by the MOE hence the student is not disadvantaged in terms of teaching and learning process.

Further findings on effectiveness of Withdrawal of privilege shows that the respondents approved the use of withdrawal of privileges teachers mean rating 3.36 and administrators mean rating 3.38 as effective approach in the management of students' discipline in secondary schools. Qualitative analysis was from students' focus group discussions like S11 who said that 'Students who misbehave should be denied the opportunity to do what they would like to do, like going to play in the field and are made to do more class work instead'.

5.2.7. S20 noted that

Students who engaged in behavioral problems were denied privileges. For instance, a member of the student leadership was demoted for being a persistent latecomer while others were denied tea for failing to carry out duties allocated to them

5.2.8. Similarly, SC1 also added that

Students should be demoted from student leadership when they break into fellow student's suitcase with an intention of stealing. Furthermore, students who were members of the student council and were engaged in boy-girl relationship were relieved of their duties as a form of punishment. Members of the student council who were involved in theft were also demoted.

The findings from the respondents shows that withdrawal of privileges was used in managing student discipline. Similarly, Kiggundu (2009) argues that there is need for withdrawal of privileges' and should be done uniformly as a discipline code which will assist parents, students and other stakeholders to appreciate the role of punishment in schools. The findings concur with study by Kilonzo, (2013), who noted that students who exhibited disciplines were

denied certain privileges with the aim of achieving behavior change in them. Maphosa (2011) established that withdrawal of privileges like demotion was commonly used in managing major forms of student disciplines. Even though the findings on withdrawal of privileges used in managing disciplines, the method didn't appear to effect behavior change uniformly among students since those who were not in student leadership would not commit the same offence as those in leadership.

For this to work well, the privileges to be withdrawn should be those that students cherish and only to students with behavior challenges and this should be done on a temporary basis so that it serves as a lesson both to offender as well as the rest of the student body. Lastly findings on effectiveness of manual work to indiscipline student shows that there was an agreement on the effectiveness of use of manual work as a corrective measure of indiscipline students by teachers mean rating at 3.27 and administrators mean rating at 3.34, both agreed that it is effective, with regard to manual punishment/work, the following responses were gathered from majority in qualitative data.

5.2.9. S9 said that

students should be manually punished. For example, you may find that they are given some tasks which are very difficult to perform like; removing tree stumps in a school, actually if they engage in these actions, it sounds a message that actually students should not go against the school rules.

5.2.10. SC2 noted

according to me, physical punishment to student is effective because if you go the ways of expulsion or being expelled from school, some students enjoy going home so they will do mistakes to go home.

5.2.11. SC3

When a principal finds someone in in-disciplined behavior, this person is entitled to a manual punishment. For example, if one found stealing, this person may be forced to pay this by going to the school forest and working in the school forest the whole day or even being assigned to mop the dorm or 2 classrooms. So when such a thing is done, the student will get scared to such activity again.

5.2.12. SC1 also shared similar sentiments saying

Punishment like picking rubbish, doing flower beds, or is it called weeding flower beds. There are so many things that can be done in the school compound which cannot hurt students. Like even cleaning their class rooms, cleaning even other areas like the dormitories.

According to various studies, physical punishment can be effective, study by Mazinaw and Elinda (2012) said that physical punishment is an effective replacement to corporal punishment where a student commits a serious offence in school. Khuu (2012) supports this by further recognizing that physical punishment has better outcomes when the punishment is meted during the learners' rest-time so that they feel the pain of losing out on playtime, break- or games time. Ifeoma (2011) also adds to the debate by agreeing with the findings of the above studies, recommended that while administering the punishment, such punishments should be commensurate with the offence committed by the learner, and that teachers should not go overboard. While it is agreed that corrective approach to students' discipline is effective there is an obvious divergence when it comes to the extent and intensity of the punishment to be administered. This makes it a challenge as it does not have a uniform mode of application. Therefore, this should be done with the child at heart of not giving work that may hurt the students' hearth or bring psychological trauma.

6. Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the study makes the following conclusions.

The preventive approach was found to be effective, with the following strategies standing out as being very effective - use of students' peer counselors in handling students' discipline; pastoral care; use of student prefects; consistency in enforcing school rules and regulations; regular G/C by principals; parental involvement in student academic performance; as well as regular consultation between parents and teachers.

The corrective approach was found to be moderately effective. More specifically, aspects such as time-out for students, suspension of indiscipline students from school, expulsion of students from school, withdrawal of privileges, and manual work while use of verbal threats were found to be only moderately effective.

The study also found that the positive behavior reinforcement approach is highly effective, with certification of most disciplined students; face to face talk with students to address discipline issues; provision of tokens; and use of motivational speakers standing out as being highly effective. Other strategies that stood out as being highly effective include monetary rewards to well-behaved students; use of praise on students with good behavior and giving monetary rewards to well-behaved students. Finally, the study concludes that principal's attitude, parental involvement in indiscipline cases, principals' experience, communication channels, policy guidelines, teacher involvement and school size influence the effectiveness of disciplinary approaches.

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